

The UNESCO World Atlas of Languages as a Tool for Promoting Brazilian Linguistic Diversity /

O Atlas UNESCO das Línguas do Mundo como instrumento de divulgação da diversidade linguística brasileira

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ABSTRACT

The dissemination of scientific knowledge has long been a secondary or even neglected aspect within the academic sphere. To overcome this scenario, scientific dissemination has gradually emerged as a movement for transmitting scientific knowledge in a unidirectional and vertical model, in which the scientist assumes the role of sender and the general public that of receiver. More recently, however, scientific dissemination has progressed toward a dialogical and participatory approach – namely, a bidirectional and horizontal model. The field of Linguistics, however, still faces challenges due to its historical constitution as a science marked by the distancing of those considered laypersons. In this context, UNESCO World Atlas of Languages emerges as an instrument for the popularization of linguistic knowledge, promoting awareness of linguistic diversity and the participation of a previously overlooked public. Thus, this article aims to discuss UNESCO World Atlas of Languages as a tool for the popularization of Linguistics, specifically regarding its methodology of collaborative production between researchers and the non-linguist public – a public that often consists of speakers of marginalized languages under the monolingual conception established and reinforced in Brazil.

KEYWORDS: *Scientific Dissemination; Linguistics Popularization; UNESCO Atlas; Linguistic Diversity.*

RESUMO

A difusão do conhecimento científico foi, por muito tempo, um aspecto secundário ou até negligenciado na esfera acadêmica. Com vistas a superar esse cenário, a divulgação científica emerge, gradativamente, como um movimento de transmissão do conhecimento científico em um modelo unidirecional e vertical, no qual o cientista assume o papel de emissor e o público em geral, de receptor. Mais recentemente, a divulgação científica tem progredido para uma abordagem dialógica e participativa – ou seja, um modelo bidirecional e horizontal. O campo da Linguística, no entanto, ainda enfrenta desafios em razão de sua constituição como ciência historicamente marcada pelo distanciamento daqueles considerados leigos. Nessa conjuntura, o Atlas UNESCO das Línguas do Mundo surge como instrumento de popularização do conhecimento linguístico, promovendo a conscientização da diversidade linguística e a participação do público antes menosprezado. Dessa forma, pretende-se abordar, neste artigo, o Atlas UNESCO das Línguas do Mundo como ferramenta de popularização da linguística, mais especificamente acerca de sua metodologia de produção colaborativa entre pesquisadores e o público não linguista – público este composto, muitas vezes, por falantes de línguas minorizadas sob a concepção de monolinguismo instaurada e consagrada no Brasil.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: *Divulgação Científica; Popularização da Linguística; Atlas UNESCO; Diversidade Linguística.*

1 Introduction

The construction of scientific knowledge through a process of publication and circulation is not a recent phenomenon. Historically, this method has not only contributed to the advancement of academic research but has also enabled the development of science through the recording and preservation of knowledge. However, it is evident that, on a large scale, this knowledge remained confined to the academic sphere, alienating the general population from both the construction process and access to the resulting production.

In an effort to break away from this methodology, *scientific dissemination* emerged as an attempt to bring the knowledge produced in the academic sphere closer to society. Initially, this process was carried out predominantly in a unidirectional model (Flores; Gomes, 2014; Marcuzzo, 2024) – that is, in a single and vertical direction. More recently, however, scientific dissemination

has gone beyond the mere transmission of information to a supposedly lay audience. This new perspective opens doors for the general population not only to have full access to knowledge but also to contribute through participation in a bidirectional model (Flores; Gomes, 2014), establishing a horizontal relationship of production.

Linguistics, as a relatively new field of scientific knowledge, still faces challenges in its popularization. This is because, according to Rajagopalan (2003), Linguistics emerged in a movement opposing the common-sense thinking prevalent at the time in the treatment of language. Consequently, the combination of the distancing of linguists and the exclusion of non-linguist individuals has resulted in these individuals becoming “increasingly isolated and viewed as having little or nothing to contribute” (Rajagopalan, 2003, p. 102, translated by the authors)¹.

In this context, the UNESCO World Atlas of Languages emerges as an essential tool for the popularization of linguistic knowledge, as it not only conveys information about linguistic diversity but also incorporates the concept of science popularization by bringing the knowledge of non-linguist public into linguistic research. Therefore, this article aims to discuss how linguistic popularization occurs within the scope of the UNESCO World Atlas of Languages and how it benefits not only the field of Linguistics as a science but also the formation of public opinion that can foster actions in language planning and language policies.

Thus, it is worth highlighting the importance of the UNESCO Atlas in linguistic dissemination at both global and regional levels, since the scientific information regarding Brazilian languages disseminated through the platform can encourage the development of a range of language policies and public policies aimed at languages that are often marginalized under the perception that Brazil is a monolingual country, which does not reflect the reality evidenced by the diversity of indigenous, immigrant, Afro-Brazilian, and sign languages present within the national territory.

2 The popularization of Science and Linguistics

The popularization of knowledge is not limited to the mere indiscriminate dissemination of information. Making it popular implies intentionality: how, why, and to whom the information will be

¹ Source: “cada vez mais isolados e vistos como quem pouco ou nada têm para contribuir”.

transmitted. In the field of scientific knowledge, the notion of science popularization may suggest something distant from everyday life, marked by complex terminologies and accessible only to specialists. However, the process of democratizing science transcends this perspective, requiring strategies that make its concepts understandable and socially relevant in order to promote development in areas such as technological innovation, cultural and historical preservation, education, public engagement and awareness, and to ensure citizenship.

Grillo, Giering, and Motta-Roth (2016) address scientific dissemination as a dynamic and interdependent discourse between science and society. The authors discuss different approaches to the dissemination of scientific discourse based on a literature review on the topic. The pioneering approach of Authier-Revuz (1998 [1982]) considers the act of modifying scientific discourse into a more popular and media-friendly discourse as a process of translation² that requires reformulation to be understood. This reformulation takes into account metalinguistic elements and features that can create barriers between the discourse of specialists and the lay public, resulting in a heterogeneous discourse that “re-establishes the broken dialogue between the scientific community and the public sphere” (Grillo; Giering; Motta-Roth, 2016, p. 4, translated by the authors)³. According to the author, two types of discourse coexist within the context of scientific dissemination: the scientific discourse, which is precise, rational, and erudite and occurs among specialists, and the everyday discourse, which is uncertain and approximate. Cataldi (2007) suggests a similar view, according to which scientific dissemination consists of “a continuous reformulative process” where scientific discourse is reformulated for specific audiences and involves three discursive procedures: expansion, as a way of adding information to facilitate understanding; reduction, which involves eliminating irrelevant technical details; and variation, which entails changing the form of presentation of scientific discourse (Grillo; Giering; Motta-Roth, 2016, p. 6, translated by the authors).

In contrast, the authors mention Zamboni (2001), who argues that the reported discourse proposed by Authier-Revuz (1998 [1982]), that is, the reformulated and translated discourse for the lay public, is not exclusive to scientific dissemination but is also present in other discourse genres, such as journalistic, political, or legal discourse, for instance. Furthermore, Zamboni argues that

² Despite similar perspectives, it should not be confused with the concept of *knowledge translation*, which is widely disseminated in the health sciences. For more details on this concept, see Reis (2019).

³ Source: “coloca em contato o diálogo rompido entre a comunidade científica e a esfera pública”.

scientists' discourse already undergoes a process of simplification before reaching diverse audiences and that scientific dissemination is a specific genre of discourse that adapts science for the lay public. While Authier-Revuz (1998 [1982]) understands discursive heterogeneity as the simultaneity between scientific discourse and everyday discourse, Zamboni (2001) analyzes how the disseminator, normally characterized by the journalistic media, actively works on scientific discourse. In other words, while the former defends discourse heterogeneity as an interaction between different voices, the latter sees it also as a creative and active process of the dissemination medium, which shapes scientific information to make it comprehensible to the public.

Additionally, Grillo, Giering, and Motta-Roth (2016) present the views of Charaudeau (2008), who emphasizes that scientific dissemination is not translation but a construction dependent on media staging, and of Grillo (2013), who, through the lens of Bakhtinian metalinguistics, proposes that scientific dissemination is a process of dialogical mediation between the scientific sphere and other spheres of society, highlighting the importance of the cultural and ideological context in the public's reception of science.

Overall, all these definitions underscore the goal of disseminating scientific knowledge in a way that reaches different social strata, ensuring its understanding and applicability through a process of democratizing information. In the literature, this process is referred to as *access to information* (see Pereira; Koshiyama, 2017), mainly linked to the rights to citizenship and information.

Supported by both domestic law – expressed, for example, in Article 5, item XXXIII, of the 1988 Brazilian Constitution – and international law – as provided, for example, in Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights –, access to information constitutes a *fundamental right* to promote and guarantee citizenship, as it enables individuals not inserted into the scientific sphere to participate in an informed manner in decision-making processes that affect their lives, including those related to language management.

Thus, it is understood, in agreement with Brambilla (2015, p. 107, translated by the authors), that “the democratization of societies is also built through the democratization of information, knowledge, and the formulation and debate of ideas.” However, access to information goes far beyond the passive action of those who produce scientific knowledge: it requires active *public communication work*.

In this context, Piccoli (2023) establishes that public communication concerns the different ways of bringing science closer to society so that scientific knowledge is understood and valued by the non-specialized public. The author presents three models through which this communication can occur: the *deficit* model, where information is transmitted didactically and unilaterally, that is, from the scientist to the public; the *complex deficit* model, in which, besides the transmission of information, the public must value scientific knowledge; and the *democratic* model, where interactive and participatory communication takes place, and knowledge is collectively built (Piccoli, 2023).

To disseminate and popularize science, it is essential to consider the means that make it possible. Thus, we can highlight scientific dissemination occurring through conferences, oral communications, colloquia, exhibitions, academic journals, etc. However, Marcuzzo (2024) explains that such actions do not fall under the popularization of scientific knowledge since they are “addressed, produced, and consumed within another sphere of human communication – the academic-scientific sphere” (Marcuzzo, 2024, p. 60, translated by the authors)⁴. Therefore, it is up to the journalistic sphere to distribute this knowledge to the general or non-specialized public. In this article, we go beyond this perspective by assigning this role not only to the journalistic sphere but also to public policies and fostering organizations that aim for the continuous improvement of science and technology, such as the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO).

Historically, Marcuzzo (2024) presents three phases of science popularization. In the first, beginning in the 17th century, science went through a process of public acceptance, mainly involving scientists and scientific associations that transmitted scientific knowledge to the general public, from those who held knowledge to those considered ignorant of the subject. In the second phase, in the 20th century, the public began to be emphasized and not merely considered scientifically ignorant; however, active participation in popularization did not occur, as the process continued to flow from science to society – this period became known as “public understanding of science.” In this phase, science reached society, but there were no effective social actions considering the popularized knowledge.

⁴ Source: “endereçados, produzidos e consumidos em outra esfera de comunicação humana – a esfera acadêmico-científica”.

Finally, in the third phase, there is a break in the unidirectional process of knowledge production, allowing public participation in science, marked by the movement of “public understanding of science,” and making popularization increasingly socialized with the advancement of information technologies and interactive media that integrate science into people's daily lives (Marcuzzo, 2024, p. 61, translated by the authors)⁵. Moreover, Marcuzzo (2024) highlights that the goals of science popularization reach three spheres: i) the educational, which involves the production and mastery of knowledge to make science more understandable and accessible; ii) the civic, which allows for the formation of public opinion; and iii) popular mobilization, in which society actively participates in the formulation of public policies (Marcuzzo, 2024).

As previously mentioned, science popularization deals with the dissemination of scientific knowledge to other social strata in a horizontal model. It is, in a way, science built by the people. Linguistics, on the other hand, “arose as a science out of a certain rejection of common-sense thinking about language” (Rajagopalan, 2003, p. 102, translated by the authors)⁶, resulting in the exclusion of the general public. Established as a scientific discipline at the beginning of the 20th century, initially grounded in the publication of Ferdinand de Saussure’s *Course in General Linguistics*, Linguistics has historically faced a paradox: although everyone uses language daily, there is a considerable gap between the production of scientific knowledge about languages and popular conceptions of language.

However, this distance has been gradually reduced in recent years through initiatives that seek to make linguistic knowledge accessible and relevant to different social strata, especially through work addressing aspects of linguistic education (see Alves *et al.*, 2022) and involving digital platforms as means of dissemination (see Hochsprung, 2023). This construction of linguistic knowledge that values both scientific knowledge and the knowledge of linguistic communities represents an important advance in this direction. By recognizing that speakers have valuable knowledge about their own languages, contemporary linguistic research can adopt more inclusive and participatory approaches, allowing knowledge production to become a more horizontal and democratic process.

In this sense, it can be assumed that linguistics is present in the three spheres of scientific dissemination (Marcuzzo, 2024), namely: in the *educational* sphere, by promoting, for example,

⁵ Source: “entendimento público da ciência”.

⁶ Source: “se ergueu como ciência a partir de um certo repúdio ao senso comum a respeito da linguagem”.

multilingual education policies and the valorization of indigenous and sign languages in schools; in the *civic* sphere, by supporting discussions about rights, accessibility, and linguistic and social inclusion; and in *popular mobilization*, by fostering initiatives to preserve endangered languages and recognize linguistic diversity. Thus, the popularization of linguistics can result in actions aimed at promoting and guaranteeing citizenship for populations from different social strata, many of whom are subject to linguistic marginalization.

Within these concepts, this article understands the role of UNESCO in the popularization of linguistic knowledge as critical, given that the organization provides the online platform of the UNESCO World Atlas of Languages and makes it public and accessible to various social layers, sharing information about the linguistic landscape of its Member States – along with the relevance of the UNESCO Chair on Language Policies for Multilingualism, which coordinates the project for the Brazilian Languages Section.

Thus, the next section will address the methodology of the UNESCO World Atlas of Languages to discuss how the scientific information collected by researchers involved in the project reaches different social layers. In addition to the lay public, this information can reach governmental bodies of UNESCO Member States and contribute to understanding linguistic situations and developing public policies related to language issues in each nation-state.

3 The UNESCO Atlas

The *UNESCO World Atlas of Languages*⁷ is a public, online platform that aims to document the spoken and sign languages of UNESCO Member States through a multidimensional approach. The tool showcases global linguistic diversity by offering a vast collection of both quantitative and qualitative language data. The *World Atlas of Languages* (hereinafter referred to as WAL) emerged in 2014, based on a pre-existing UNESCO project, the *Atlas of the World's Languages in Danger*, which had three editions (1996, 2001, and 2010) aimed to map as many endangered languages as possible worldwide using UNESCO's vitality scale. The last edition was available in an online

⁷ The *World Atlas of Languages* online platform is available at: <https://en.wal.unesco.org/world-atlas-languages>. Accessed on: 17 feb. 2025.

format, accessible not only to specialists but also to the interested public. With the WAL, the focus has shifted and a large amount of languages are now documented (Romeira, 2024).

In Brazil specifically, the WAL falls under the responsibility of the UNESCO Chair on Language Policies for Multilingualism (hereinafter referred to as UCLPM), hosted at the Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC) in Florianópolis and coordinated by Professor PhD. Gilvan Müller de Oliveira. The UCLPM encompasses 17 countries, 34 universities, specialized networks, institutes, and more. The Chair maintains agreements with universities across the country. In this way, just as the UCLPM operates as an integrated network supported by various researchers, the WAL is also presented as a collaborative project.

The WAL platform hosts data collected through a questionnaire designed to gather information on the *size, status, affiliation, functions, and users of languages*. Developed by a specialized UNESCO team, the questionnaire comprises 30 questions for spoken languages and 27 for sign languages. According to Sarate (2024), the questions are interrelated and can be categorized as follows: i) *questions about the language*, of a qualitative nature, regarding status, genetic affiliation, availability of materials, etc.; ii) *questions about language users*, from a more quantitative perspective, addressing the number of speakers, their proportion within the total population and the reference community; iii) *questions about the language's dimension*, discussing sociogeographic and socioeconomic scope; and iv) *questions about language use*, from a qualitative perspective, covering its presence in administration, formal education, and other spaces.

The questionnaire responses, later added to the platform, are provided by researchers working with the language or community in collaboration with at least one speaker of the language. Thus, speakers are protagonists alongside researchers, offering more precise information, especially for languages with little existing academic research. This approach promotes active participation in the production of scientific knowledge, consolidating the principle of horizontal and bidirectional knowledge production. This enables not only the development of public opinion about the languages being researched but also actively engages speaker communities. Sarate (2024) also notes that the questionnaire encourages inclusion of all available information about a language, even if it comes from non-academic sources, emphasizing that unofficial generated data are valuable for building scientific knowledge through active societal participation.

Considering the many advantages of the WAL platform in the context of global linguistic diversity, it is worth highlighting that, in Brazil, its relevance is fundamental, since the State does

not have a digital tool offering comprehensive and consolidated data on Brazilian languages. Although Linguistics and other Human Sciences fields investigate languages or marginalized communities, these studies often focus on specific aspects. Meanwhile, the WAL provides a broad panorama of each language, allowing an understand of its vitality in an integrated and accessible way. Thus, the information complements each other and, precisely because it is gathered in a single place, it presents a simplified view for the general public the factors that strengthen or weaken a language.

The WAL delivers a series of unprecedented data about Brazilian languages. One of the most significant contributions is the number of speakers for each language. Currently, the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) census includes only indigenous languages. Through the WAL, we will have this data for other language groups as well. According to Muller (2009), Brazil is home to more than 200 languages, including immigrant languages, sign languages, indigenous languages, among others. Therefore, the WAL platform reveals Brazil's rich linguistic diversity, previously confined to academic circles and a specialized audience, and often unknown even to speakers of minority languages. With the WAL, this information is centralized on an open-access platform, allowing a clear, didactic visualization of the data and encouraging the participation of all interested parties.

In a country like Brazil, where the idea of monolingualism was historically promoted through the Portuguese language as a symbol of nationalism, bringing this information to light enhances public awareness about linguistic diversity, drawing attention not only to indigenous languages – which have recently gained visibility after being constitutionally recognized in 1988 and subsequently taught in local indigenous schools – but also to immigrant languages, which have been gradually gaining recognition through municipal and state co-officialization movements⁸.

Also in terms of the benefits of popularizing data on languages of Brazil, we highlight that the WAL platform also makes visible languages that may need greater attention from the State and, therefore, public policies. Many languages have few speakers and are losing functional domains, revealing the urgent need for language revitalization policies – a field still underexplored in Brazil. These data will later provide a broader overview of Brazilian languages and can even be used to

⁸ For more information regarding the co-officialization of languages in Brazil at the municipal and state levels, see Heine and Penkal (2024) and Rabelo, Simas, and Oliveira (2024), respectively. To access the database of legal norms responsible for the co-officialization of languages in Brazil, consult the Brazilian Repository of Language Legislation (Matos, 2024).

alert communities themselves of the risk of their language disappearing. By offering data such as speaker numbers and generational transmission rates, for instance, it becomes possible to coordinate actions among researchers, public institutions, and speaker communities to promote and value these languages, facilitating communication and discussions on intervention strategies. These initiatives could take the form of social movements, co-officialization laws, the production of materials, informational booklets, and more, always in collaboration with speaker communities.

Aligned with this perspective, the WAL also addresses language presence in cyberspace, raising awareness of the need to equip languages for online presence, not only in personal communication media, such as *WhatsApp* or *Telegram*, but also on social networks, thus broadening language circulation, which can, over time, gain space and become stronger in the community itself and in the world, since there are no borders in the cyberspace. Currently, in Brazil, 58 immigrant and indigenous languages are co-official at municipal and state levels (Matos, 2024). However, most of these languages still lack digital resources such as online translators, which could jeopardize their vitality. In this context, we believe that the panorama provided by the WAL, by pointing out the lack of these languages in the media, can serve as a wake-up call and encouragement for communities to expand language use across different domains and foster linguistic valorization social movements.

In Brazil, UCLPM conducts data collection alongside native speakers of the languages. Community representatives are invited to take part and, with the researchers, can generate accurate data to answer the questionnaire, becoming researchers of the language themselves. This integrated work connects academia directly with communities, popularizing linguistic knowledge and emphasizing that the non-academic knowledge of speakers – embedded in community life and language use – is extremely important to that language vitality, since non-academic knowledge is also considered essential and fully embraced in the WAL methodology.

In the Brazilian section of WAL, questionnaires are currently being completed by anyone interested in participating. The project also relies on key partnerships, such as the UFSC Working Group on the Geopolitics of Multilingualism, linked to UCLPM, and the International Decade of Indigenous Peoples, which maintains the dialogue between indigenous language speakers and researchers, among countless other professionals who cooperate in the arduous task of popularizing knowledge about Brazil's linguistic diversity. In a country like Brazil, where monolingual ideologies prevail and little attention is given to linguistic diversity, the WAL platform highlights

necessary actions and serves as an alert not just to some government agencies or specific audiences, but extends to the entire Brazilian society.

Thus, the WAL platform emerges as an essential contemporary digital resource that enables not only diagnosing linguistic diversity but also (re)thinking language policies – or the lack of them – through a comparative lens, observing strategies adopted by different countries for language promotion. Moreover, ensuring that this information is open and accessible to all audiences is crucial, and through the WAL, this becomes possible, as the website maintains open data with active participation from language speakers themselves, empowering communities that often have little or no access to information about their own languages.

Final Considerations

Scientific dissemination has been progressively evolving from a unidirectional and vertical model, which transmits scientific knowledge to society, to a more bidirectional and horizontal approach that values the active participation of society in its production. In this context, Linguistics, as a scientific field consolidated for about a century, has sought to develop strategies to overcome its historical distancing and to reach various social layers, sharing its knowledge across educational, civic, and popular mobilization spheres. More recently, the *World Atlas of Languages* (WAL) has been dedicated to the popularization of linguistic knowledge through data generated by its collaborative and participatory methodology and through its open and digital availability to the public.

Thus, the WAL promotes joint research between researchers and speakers from linguistic communities and makes available, on a UNESCO digital platform, data on the dimension, status, affiliation, functions, and users of languages, allowing a non-specialized audience to access information about the linguistic diversity of UNESCO Member States. Furthermore, the section dedicated to Brazilian languages, coordinated by the UNESCO Chair on Language Policies for Multilingualism, opens doors for future actions in language planning and policy for the multilingual scenario of Brazil, which has an invaluable diversity of indigenous, immigrant, Afro-Brazilian, sign languages, among others.

However, although the dissemination and popularization of linguistics are essential not only for expanding access to scientific knowledge in the field across different social layers but also for

building a more participatory science, these initiatives still face limitations, as there is a clear lack of studies that expand theoretical and practical discussions on the topic. In addition, there is a noticeable shortage of linguistic research that engages in dialogue with communities and makes them protagonists during the process.

Thus, we hope that this article can contribute to future research on scientific dissemination and the popularization of linguistics aimed at highlighting the participatory character of knowledge production and promoting it across the most varied fields of activity, such as linguistic diversity, for instance. Promoting linguistic diversity in countries like Brazil is an indispensable step in guaranteeing citizenship to speakers who may face barriers in accessing essential services due to their language. Therefore, it is crucial that new research expands the popularization of linguistic knowledge to ensure that studies in the field reach different audiences and become part of every citizen's life through the joint production of knowledge.

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